

Introducing the PHOTONIC project: mainstreaming smart data access for photon sources users

Dan Allan⁶, Devin Burke¹, Patrick Fuhrmann¹, Shruti Ghargi¹, Christian Gutt³, Nicolas Hayen⁴, Thomas Michelat², Paul Millar¹, Bridget Murphy^{1,2}, Sebastian Paripisa¹, Linus Pithan¹, Andre Rothkirch¹, Sophie Servan¹, Ajit Seth², William Smith⁵, Peter van der Reest¹, and Tim Wetzel¹

¹*Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY*

²*Kiel University*

³*Siegen University*

⁴*European XFEL*

⁵*Helmholtz Center Berlin HZB*

⁶*Brookhaven National Laboratory*

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Abstract

The Erum-Data initiative of the BMFTR promotes the transition from “big data” to “smart data.” The PHOTONIC project addresses this goal for photon science by enabling selective, efficient access to experimental data, initially targeting external users of DESY beamlines, particularly university groups.

PHOTONIC aims to provide live and offline access to whole or sliced data, in user-defined formats. It supports both on-site experiments and remote analysis by the principal investigator and their team and, ultimately, public access in the frame of the DESY data policy [1]. Key use cases include X-ray reflectivity, requiring low-latency feedback, and X-ray photon correlation spectroscopy, characterised by high data volumes with smaller regions of interest.

The project started on November 1, 2025, and the team has now grown to near completion. The project infrastructure is in place and we have begun evaluating *Tiled* [2], as the existing software upon which we are building. *Tiled* is an open-source scientific data access platform already adopted at several synchrotrons, including at Diamond Light Source and Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin for pilot beamlines.

The official kick-off meeting was held at DESY on March 6, 2026, with participation from European XFEL, University of Kiel, University of Siegen, Helmholtz Center Berlin, and Brookhaven National Laboratory.

1 Introduction

PHOTONIC is a recently launched ErUM-Data project that aims to make photon science data more accessible through selective, remote, and standardised access mechanisms. Building on existing developments in scientific data management, we seek to enable users to access complete datasets or only the specific data slices required for their analysis, both during and after an experiment.

Today, photon science users often rely on facility-specific workflows, manual data transfers, and delayed access to experimental results. Through PHOTONIC, we address these limitations by developing a common framework for smart data access, enabling data and metadata to be accessed through standard interfaces and integrated directly into scientific analysis environments.

This article serves as a first project report following the official PHOTONIC kick-off meeting held at DESY on 6 March 2026. We introduce the project consortium, outline the initial technical

roadmap, present the work packages, and summarise the first implementation activities and discussions that will guide the project’s first year.

1.1 What makes PHOTONIC distinctive?

Several factors position PHOTONIC for success and will guide the project throughout its life-time.

Origin. The project was initiated from requirements expressed by photon science user communities, particularly university groups, rather than from a technology-first perspective. The scientific use cases therefore serve as the primary driver for architectural and technical decisions throughout the project.

Timing. The project starts at a time when several developments are converging: the transition between the first and second funding phases of DAPHNE4NFDI [3], the completion of ROCK-IT [4], and at a cornerstone of the preparation of PETRA IV [5]. It develops in parallel to the building of a federated EOSC, in which we are involved both thematically with the PaNOSC Node and nationally with the NFDI Node.

People. (i) The founding mothers and fathers – Christian Gutt, Bridget Murphy, and Linus Pithan – are taking an active part in the project. (ii) EuXFEL and HZB participate as active observers and volunteers for adoption beyond DESY. (iii) We were very lucky with our new recruits – Sebastian Paripsa, Shruti Ghargi, and Ajit Seth – bringing strong expertise in both scientific applications and software development. And finally (iv) a close collaboration with *Tiled* has been established already thanks to Dan Allan, Devin Burke, and the openness of the Bluesky community.

Adoption. We are in a favourable position to ensure long-term adoption of our service through HIFIS, EOSC nodes and PETRA IV. Alongside active outreach through conference participation, we are already invited to important events and benefit from a prior network we’ve been building through HIFIS and PaNOSC.

1.2 Technical roadmap

This collaborative project between photon science user groups and DESY-IT introduces a new approach to accessing photon science data: real-time, online, and standardised. Building on prior work, we resolve standardisation gaps and establish a corresponding service at DESY to be rolled out to associated partners. The overall architecture is presented in Figure 1.

For the first project year, we focus on a minimum viable product for already catalogued data. This allows us to evaluate the most critical architectural questions before extending the system to live data streams. These questions include storage access from *Kubernetes* [6], federated authentication and authorisation, security for non-public data, and end-to-end performance of selective data access.

Figure 1: PHOTONIC architecture

The main steps are so far defined as follows:

- First *Tiled* deployment ready for demonstration and testing
 - *Kubernetes* cluster created and ready for deployment (*completed*)
 - First vanilla *Tiled* deployment (*completed*)
 - Demonstration data source available for testing *Tiled*
- Evaluate storage mounting options for *Kubernetes*
- Evaluate AAI connection options
- First client software deployed
- Create dedicated volume in `photonic-prod` for client developers
- Test and evaluate streaming via websockets

These checkpoints are targeting in particular the two following risks:

1. **Security.** Exposing data that is not yet open carries risks. We need to start negotiating with all actors involved early on, while looking for robust technical solutions. In the meantime, we can experiment extensively with open data. Gradually, we will move to dummy private data and ultimately to embargoed data.
2. **Performance.** We do not yet know if running *Tiled* in *Kubernetes* provides fast enough access to storage. This needs to be determined soon, so that the infrastructure can be adapted if necessary. We anticipate performance tests to be carried out with P08, P10, XFEL MID and P02.1, to cover different data streams.

2 Work packages

At the project kick-off, WP leaders (Table 1) had an opportunity to present their plan.

2.1 Coordination & project management

The project management team aims to support a qualitative and timely delivery of project outputs and to maintain good communication channels and processes. As shown in Table 2, the

WP	Name	Lead
1	Coordination	Sophie Servan (DESY)
2	Back-end services, data access	Devin Burke (DESY)
3	Data formats and transcoding	Paul Millar (DESY)
4	Use cases and client tool integration	Bridget Murphy (Kiel)
5	Dissemination, outreach and training	(Siegen)

Table 1: PHOTONIC work packages

project management infrastructure is now in place, completing the first PHOTONIC milestone.

All tools are hosted either by DESY, or HIFIS through the Helmholtz Cloud [7] and are open source. Access rights are organised either via Helmholtz ID directly or through the PHOTONIC user group. The evolving project infrastructure has a fixed and public landing page [8] that lists all project-related tools and their corresponding policies.

Tool	Purpose
GitLab (<i>partially restricted</i>)	Landing page for project tools, issue tracking, and project timeline
Mailing lists at photonic-project.org (<i>partially restricted</i>)	info : contact email core : core team of contributors all : contributors and observers
Indico	Events and workshops management, calendar
SyncandShare (<i>restricted</i>)	Shared project documentation
HedgeDoc (<i>restricted</i>)	Live collaborative note taking
Let's meet	Video conferencing

Table 2: Overview of project management tooling and their access policy.

A scientific advisory board will be set up for the project to ensure that external advisors can monitor project development and decisions. Given the project's size and scope, we intend to keep the board relatively informal and lightweight in terms of process, focusing on mid-level management members from photon sources and beyond.

During the kick-off meeting, we identified an opportunity for our first annual meeting and acted upon it unanimously. We have decided to hold the first all-hands meeting immediately after the NOBUGS conference [9] in Hamburg, on 28 September 2026, securing the participation of *Tiled* developers.

2.2 Back-end services, data access

WP2 is responsible for the back-end services that connect PHOTONIC to facility infrastructure (Figure 2). The central goal is to provide a remote API through which users and client applications can access experimental data in an authenticated, selective, and standardised way.

The first implementation focuses on *Tiled* deployments on DESY *Kubernetes* infrastructure. These deployments are used to test access to representative datasets, including partial reads such as small regions of interest from large detector images. This is essential for reducing unnecessary data movement and for enabling interactive analysis from remote sites.

Several infrastructure questions are being evaluated in parallel. These include access from *Kubernetes* to facility storage systems, comparison of storage backends and the integration of authentication and authorisation mechanisms compatible with HIFIS (Helmholtz ID) and EOSC

environments. Security is treated as a staged process: development starts with open data, then progresses to synthetic private data, and eventually to embargoed experimental datasets.

A further objective of WP2 is to provide an early public or semi-public deployment for local users and client-tool developers. This allows feedback to be collected before the system is extended to more demanding use cases, including live data access.

Opinionated choices with regards to the architecture will be documented in *GitLab* issues [10].

Figure 2: PHOTONIC infrastructure

2.3 Data formats and transcoding

Data-driven scientific investigation requires access to both the underlying observations (data) and sufficient information about how those observations were made (metadata). This information is recorded in files that, to achieve interoperability and reuse of software, follow specific file formats and metadata conventions.

The available portfolio of file formats and metadata standards is not static, multiple solutions exist. These differences may arise from satisfying different use-cases, or it may demonstrate an evolution as new file formats or metadata standards address limitations of earlier approaches.

Analysis and visualisation software cannot support all possible file formats. This can lead to problems when working with data because the best software might not support the data format provided by the beamline. This places the researchers in a difficult position: whether to convert the data manually slowing down the access to data, or to use less capable software.

Within the PHOTONIC project’s WP3, we are cataloguing the available file formats and approaches to metadata across the target beamlines, along with the desired scientific use-cases and the software that supports those use-cases. With this determination, we can identify where it makes sense to convert data from one file to a different file format, or recast the metadata into a different schema. We implement these capacities at the server side: see transcoding plugins in Figure 1.

Since there is likely to be no single ”best” solution, we investigate having some common representation into which requested data may be converted, and from which we can convert the data into the desired format.

Such an approach may find use outside of the PHOTONIC project; for example, the data translation could also operate as a universal data-translation tool when applied to files [11]. The

tool could also check that files conform to the desired format and provide sufficient metadata to support the intended analysis.

We align our work with previous and ongoing activities, including the consolidation efforts carried out within the OSCARS project [12], as well as standardisation work conducted by the NFDI FAIRmat consortium [13].

Most importantly, we will engage with domain experts and beamline scientists throughout the project.

Candidate formats and their inclusion in the transcoding modules (or not) will be documented as issues in *GitLab*. For example and as discussed during the kick-off, event-based data formats and awkward arrays – which are in *Tiled* timeline – will be included as candidates.

2.4 Use cases and client tool integration

The primary objective of WP4 is to provide and test a user-friendly interface, building upon the initial *Tiled* deployments, to bridge the gap between the unified PHOTONIC API and the diverse scientific software ecosystem.

As illustrated in the general architecture (Figure 1), the API Client at universities is planned to serve as the critical functional link that enables researchers to perform remote and slice-based data evaluation. This eventually eliminates the necessity of manual bulk data transfers.

Our efforts focus on the facilitation of smart data access through the integration of client libraries into established community software such as H5Web or silx-kit [14]. This ensures a standardised entry point that reduces the reliance on manual data handling and facilitates ad-hoc scientific analysis.

2.4.1 Reflectometry

The study of interfacial phenomena using X-ray reflectivity (XRR) is dependent on the development of tools for the precise extraction of electron density profiles and the extracting molecular-level structural details from complex interfaces.

In the case of XRR, data chunking is often secondary to the requirement of viewing an entire detector image to precisely identify and select multiple regions of interest (ROIs).

For the particular use case, we intend to implement high-resolution visualisation for specific ROIs within the large detector images. The initial implementation focuses on utilizing the LISA instrument [15] at the beamline P08 (PETRA III) as a primary demonstrator for live data access. A key objective in this use case is to enable researchers to seamlessly jump between datasets to compare current experimental runs with legacy data, such as those catalogued in the Gamma portal or SciCat [16].

Furthermore, we aim to integrate the ORSO ASCII standard to ensure that legacy datasets remain fully interoperable within the modern framework [17].

2.4.2 XPCS

X-ray photon correlation spectroscopy (XPCS) provides a critical test for the PHOTONIC framework due to the massive data volumes and high acquisition rates inherent to modern instruments like Materials Imaging and Dynamics (MID) at European XFEL, which is also adapted for P10 (PETRA III).

Currently, the integration of the Python-based extra-speckle [18] software at European XFEL has enabled the processing of XPCS data with minimal latency. Furthermore, preliminary workflows using the DAMNIT tool [19, 20] have been established to trigger automated analysis immediately upon data migration to offline storage. This has enabled the researchers to perform

live parameter adjustments during an experiment which is a significant advancement over the traditional three-week timeline previously necessary for data evaluation.

In parallel, initial evaluations of the *Tiled* data access service are also underway to determine its efficacy in providing structured access to these high-rate data streams.

Our future efforts will focus on using the PHOTONIC API to stream specific data slices directly into analysis environments, bypassing the need for time-consuming bulk data transfers. Additionally, we intend to integrate the DAMNIT workflow engine more deeply with the project’s unified API to allow for near-real-time feedback.

To ensure long-term data sustainability, WP4 will support the ongoing community push within the NeXus International Advisory Committee (NIAC) to standardise the NeXus + XPCS format (NXxpcs application definition). This will provide a common representation for XPCS data from different facilities and reduce the need for facility-specific conversion in downstream analysis tools.

2.5 Dissemination, outreach and training

As part of WP5, we identify the following main targets for outreach activities:

1. Researchers at partner universities
2. Instrument scientists at partner institutes
3. NFDI Consortia, in particular DAPHNE4NFDI
4. Other ErUM-Data projects, in particular involving the KFS community

Our outreach plan for the first year of PHOTONIC is first to participate at events relevant to these target groups:

Date	Event	Contribution	Target group
2025-11-25	Welcome to ErUM-Data: Onboarding	Talk	4
2025-12-04	ErUM-Data Community: DIG-UM Annual Meeting 2025	Representation	4
2026-03-06	FIDIUM Collaboration and DIG-UM Federated Infrastructures Meeting 2026	Talk	4
2026-03-06	PHOTONIC kick-off	Organisation	1,2,3
2026-03-17	International Symposium on Grids & Clouds (ISGC) 2026	Talk	1
2026-03-18	Statustreffen ErUM-Data	Poster	3,4
2026-09-08	SNIB2026	<i>Abstract</i>	1,2,3,4
2026-09-21	NOBUGS 2026	<i>Abstract</i>	2
2026-09-21	EGI conference	<i>Talk</i>	1
2026-09-28	PHOTONIC Annual Meeting	<i>Organisation</i>	1,2,3,4

Table 3: Preliminary PHOTONIC event participation plan and mapping to our targets

We plan to extend outreach beyond our partners and communities in a later stage of the project.

In parallel, we have started a website to present the project at photonic-project.org [21].

WP5 will extend to training activities when the first prototypes are available. The *still-to-be-found* WP leader will steer the training plan for PHOTONIC.

3 *Tiled*

Tiled [22] is a data access and management service that is already adopted at multiple facilities worldwide, including the Australian Synchrotron, the Brazilian Synchrotron, the Canadian Light Source, Diamond Light Source, and several US Department of Energy facilities.

The project follows a multi-facility governance model with a substantial presence outside of the United States. Development is coordinated through weekly informal calls, bringing together a rotating group of 20–30 contributors from facilities worldwide, including members of our PHOTONIC development team.

Tiled enables users to search across metadata, access and slice arrays and tables remotely, and transcode data into the required formats. Data can be streamed directly into analysis programs without the need to touch disk.

The *Tiled* service was successfully deployed at DESY on a *Kubernetes* [6] cluster using a Git-Ops workflow managed through ArgoCD [23], as part of an infrastructure setup. Persistent storage was provisioned via Ceph-backed [24] Persistent Volume Claims (PVCs) within the `photonics-dev` namespace, making data available across pod restarts. The storage volume was further tested by attaching a second independent PVC. As data volume grows, it can have independent modular storage.

We explored the *Tiled* client to interact with the *Tiled* server, and access specific data slices such as a small 100x100 region of a larger image directly on demand, eliminating the need to load or download the entire dataset. A dedicated PVC was additionally created and populated with 26.5 GB of P02.1 [25] (DESY) sample data to serve as an example dataset through the *Tiled* service.

Additionally, to identify the most suitable storage back-end for *Tiled* on *Kubernetes*, we are comparing Ceph, GPFS [26]/IBM Spectrum Scale CSI driver [27], and NFS-CSI [28]; we are actively exploring layered benchmark possibilities. The result will isolate the contribution of each component, and will separate *Tiled*'s intrinsic performance from issues caused by the *Kubernetes* stack and by the storage back-end itself. Initial results show that *Tiled* itself is not a limiting factor at the scale of interest.

4 Science Traceability Matrix

Borrowed from large scientific facilities and space projects, a Science Traceability Matrix (STM) links scientific goals to technical requirements and verification criteria.

Following a suggestion by Devin Burke, we are exploring the use of an STM to define and follow requirements for PHOTONIC. While this approach is common in large engineering projects, it remains relatively unusual in photon science software and data-management initiatives. We nevertheless believe that PHOTONIC is well suited to experiment with it: the project is large enough to benefit from a structured requirements process, yet still sufficiently focused and collaborative for such a process to remain lightweight and useful.

The STM captures high-level scientific objectives and progressively breaks them down into more specific questions, capabilities, technical implementations, and verification activities. Beyond helping us define what the project should deliver, it also provides a mechanism to ensure that technical developments remain connected to scientific needs and that project scope remains under control over time.

An important goal is to make the STM a communication tool rather than merely a project-management artefact. We expect it to facilitate discussions between scientists, software developers, and infrastructure providers by making explicit the chain of reasoning that links scientific use cases to implementation decisions.

The current STM is still under development, but its structure is already emerging. For example, one of the primary scientific objectives is to enable easy data access. This objective is decomposed into a series of science questions such as:

- How can researchers access sliced data or regions of interest without transferring entire datasets?
- How can researchers find and search their data?
- How can data be transcoded into user-defined formats?
- How can researchers monitor live data streams?

Each question is then associated with operational capabilities and concrete project deliverables. For example, the requirement to access sliced datasets leads to the capability of partial data retrieval through a standardised API, which in turn maps to the development of a Direct Data Access API and corresponding transcoding modules. Similar chains can be established for live data access, metadata search, authentication and authorisation, and client-side visualisation.

As the project progresses, performance requirements, service requirements, verification criteria, and work-package responsibilities will be attached to each branch of the matrix. We expect the STM to evolve alongside the project during its first phase before stabilising into a reference document that can guide future development and assess project outcomes.

5 Stay up-to-date

If you are interested in staying up-to-date or becoming an observer for the project, feel free to reach out at `info at photonic-project.org`.

In the case you'd like to suggest a new client or a new transcoding module, please open an issue in *GitLab* [10].

All PHOTONIC-related events, either organised by us, or where we are planning to contribute with a talk or a poster are listed in our Indico category, see Table 2. You can subscribe to the calendar there.

We will be updating the website regularly from September 2026 onwards [21], including our list of publications and upcoming (training) events.

6 Summary

PHOTONIC was launched in November 2025 with the objective of enabling smart, selective, and standardised access to photon science data. Since then, the project consortium has been assembled, the technical and organisational foundations have been established, and the first deployments and evaluations of *Tiled* have begun.

During the kick-off meeting, the consortium refined the initial roadmap and identified the key challenges that will shape the first project phase. In particular, security, authentication and authorisation, storage integration, and performance of selective data access will be investigated through a first minimum viable product based on already catalogued datasets.

A central objective of PHOTONIC is to reduce the need for manual bulk data transfers and facility-specific access workflows. Instead, we aim to enable users and scientific software to access only the data and metadata required for a given task, whether during an experiment, shortly afterwards, or in the context of long-term data reuse.

By the end of the project, we will consider PHOTONIC successful if users can securely access and analyse selected slices of experimental data from multiple facilities through a common interface, without requiring manual data transfer or facility-specific solutions. Achieving this goal will

require close collaboration between researchers, beamline scientists, software developers, and infrastructure providers, which is reflected in the structure of the consortium itself.

This report marks the beginning of that journey. We look forward to sharing future developments as the project progresses.

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